

The pursuit of a Ph.D. in Biblical Studies is much more than the pursuit of academic knowledge. It is also about the pursuit of one’s relationship with the living God. At least, that is the way it is for me. I approach every class as an opportunity to sharpen my mind and my heart. My institution believes the same and requires that each student – even at a doctoral level – take spiritual formation classes. One of my spiritual formation classes required me to write four brief papers on books of the Bible. I chose the following:

Habakkuk – From Frustration to Faith
Haggai – Journal of a Jerusalem Prophet
Philemon – Earthquake in the Empire
1 John – Apostolic Apologetic

You will not find many footnotes or an extensive bibliography. These are not meant to be scholarly presentations but observations of the text and reflections of the heart. I pass them to you for your edification in mind and spirit.

Habakkuk – From Frustration to Faith

It is, arguably, one of the most profound, yet overlooked verses in the OT. The prophet, commencing his final words, said in 3:2, “O LORD, I have heard the report about you, and I fear. O LORD, revive Your work in the midst of the years, in the midst of the years make it known; in wrath remember mercy.”¹ To grasp their impact, one must understand the movement of the book.

Habakkuk was a temple musician-prophet who lived during the reign of the last kings of Judah.² He lamented the dismal state into which the people of God had sunk. Like the psalmists of old, he asked, “How long, O Lord ...?” and “Why do you ...?” The book is dialogical containing the prophet’s questions, God’s responses, and a concluding psalm of trust. It presents issues of theodicy, “Why are those who are more wicked than your people the instruments of your judgment?” When one understands the frustration, the pain, and Habakkuk’s incredulity

¹ New American Standard Bible, The Lockman Foundation, La Habra, CA, 1995.

² Boda and McConville, “Habakkuk,” J.K. Bruckner, 294-295.

over the sin of God's people and God's surprising and unsatisfying solution, the words of 3:2 which introduce his final words can be fully appreciated for their expression of trust in God.

The book divides into three sections matching the three chapters. Chapter 1 begins with Habakkuk's lamentation in 1:2-4. He is bold in his complaint to God; how long must he call for help until God does something! How long until God hears? Like a person in this modern world trying to reach the right customer service representative by phone, yet being put on hold endlessly, Habakkuk is "put on hold" by God. In the meantime, the people continue to sin which he describes in 1:3-4. Finally, God answers! God will discipline his people. He will use the Babylonian empire to wreak havoc. God does not mince his words. In 1:5-11, he describes the foe. They are fierce and impetuous. They derive justice and authority from themselves. They are arrogant, violent, and they worship military might.

Habakkuk is stunned. The Babylonians? They are more wicked than Judah! In 1:12-17, Habakkuk asks, "Why would you, God, you who are holy and who would never do anything wrong allow such a nation to 'swallow up those more righteous than they?'" Habakkuk again challenges God, this time, not for his silence but for his answer! First, it was, "God, you are not talking to me!" Now it was, "God, I don't like what you say!"

Chapter 2 begins the second part. God has answered the prophet's complaint, and although Habakkuk does not like the answer, he now knows God will speak. He stations himself upon the wall of Jerusalem and prepares for God's word. It comes again, this time in 2:2-5. Habakkuk is to record what God says. "The vision that he receives will be accomplished. He must be patient. God's word will not fail. Two kinds of people live in the world – those who are proud, like the Babylonians, and those who place their faith in the God of Israel. The just will live by faith!"

In the remainder of the chapter, the Lord pronounces five woes upon sinners in the world culminating in the unprofitability of idolatry and the contrast of worthless, lifeless idols with the living God in his temple and before whom the earth is to be silent. Sinners will be judged. They will not get away with what they are doing. The earth will be filled with the knowledge of the glory of the Lord as the waters cover the sea. God's kingdom will prevail.

The vision is over. The message is complete, but what will the complainer say? How will the one who has lamented his people's sin and God's strategy to correct his people respond? Will he be like the proud one whose soul is not right within him, or will he respond in faith? Chapter 3 provides the answer to this drama between God and his prophet. Habakkuk pens a poem of praise! He begins with the words cited in the opening paragraph. "O LORD, I have heard the report about you, and I fear. O LORD, revive Your work in the midst of the years, in the midst of the years make it known; in wrath remember mercy."

Habakkuk acknowledges that the reports he has heard about the Lord from his youth and retold in the worship of the temple are true! He thinks on all God has done in the history of his people, and he fears, he stands in awe of this God who acts on behalf of his people. As he meditates upon those works and contemplates God's fresh work in his generation, he prays that God would revive it, and even though it entails wrath upon his people – and the nations – he confidently prays for mercy. Habakkuk knows that God is not silent. God has spoken. God will act, and God will advance his plan for his people and the world even though it is a strange work in his day (1:5).

The first stanza of his song begins with theophanic descriptions of God's intervention; the radiance of the sun, lightning, plague, earthquake, and flood. But these descriptions in 3:3-8 are not generic. They were experienced by his people of old when the God of Israel worked

wonders. He affirms this in stanza 2, 3:9-13a. He confesses that God went forth for the salvation of his people. He gets more specific in stanza 3, 3:13b-15, as he describes God's victory over the forces of chaos manifested in the house of the wicked.

Habakkuk's song is nearing completion. His majestic words of praise are finished. He descends from the lofty and true expressions of God's might, but he must now face the reality of his time and his role in God's plan. Yes, God once came to this world with mighty deeds for his people, but now the Babylonians are coming, and all Habakkuk can do is to wait quietly for the day of distress, for the people to arise who will invade Judah (3:16).

But this time, Habakkuk is not complaining. This time, in 3:17-19, he praises!

Though the fig tree should not blossom
And there be no fruit on the vines,
Though the yield of the olive should fail
And the fields produce no food,
Though the flock should be cut off from the fold
And there be no cattle in the stalls,
Yet I will exult in the Lord,
I will rejoice in the God of my salvation.
The Lord God is my strength,
And He has made my feet like hinds' feet,
And makes me walk on my high places.

Yes, disaster looms and basic needs will become scarce, but Habakkuk steadies himself and moves forward in faith. He will exult in the Lord; he will rejoice for God is his strength. He completes his song, and he prepares if for the choir director. He wants everyone to sing about what he has seen and heard in his encounter with the God who is sometimes silent and with the God who often provides answers difficult to understand. But he is the God who must be trusted.

Habakkuk has passed them on to us. In his book, we find not just a beautiful psalm of praise (chapter 3), but the experiences of his encounters with God (chapters 1-2). These words

and experiences provide strength for today, and one finds encouragement by observing his struggle.

Habakkuk wailed about the sin of his people. He vigorously approached the throne of God. He questioned God's decisions and let God know how he felt. But he learned to listen to the words of the Most High and found resolution in his heart as his view of God, his wisdom, and his plan for Israel and the world expanded.

If we modern people wish for answers to the dilemmas we face, we would do well to follow Habakkuk's example. Wrestle with God honestly, listen to his full revelation, choose the path of faith, expand your awareness of his wisdom and might, praise him for his mighty deeds, and pass on what you have learned to others.

Haggai – Journal of a Jerusalem Prophet

What would it be like to discover an ancient manuscript that was the journal of a prophet of God? What would it be like to read this journal and see his thoughts as he grappled with his calling to proclaim the Word of God to the leaders and the people who had lost their focus? There is something close to that in the Bible, almost like a journal that a prophet was keeping. It is the book of Haggai. Haggai is a tiny two-chapter book tucked away in the last pages of the Old Testament, yet one finds him delivering a large message for the people of God at that time and for the people of God today.

His name means "make a pilgrimage," or "observe a pilgrimage feast," perhaps because he was born on a festival day, and if so, showing the faith of parents who were wishing to return to the land and celebrate the feasts of God.³ Besides his book, Haggai is mentioned in the book

³ Leander E. Keck, *The New Interpreter's Bible*, Vol VII, "Haggai," W. Eugene March, Abingdon, Nashville, 1996, 707.

of Ezra (5:1; 6:14), but that is all the biblical information about him. Most importantly, his message was an important word for his time and the Church today.

The style in which Haggai writes is unique to the prophets.⁴ It is almost like a journal. In the year 520 BC, for 3½ months, God gave five messages to Haggai who gives the date for each one. They begin August 29, and the last two come on December 18. In other OT prophets, one can sometimes find generalized periods. For example, Isaiah says that he prophesied during the reigns of Uzziah, Jotham, Ahaz, and Hezekiah. But one does not find anything close to Haggai's precise dating.

The historical situation into which Haggai spoke with exact dates is a reminder that God's prophets did not write as theoretical or abstract philosophers. They were real people, working in difficult, real-life situations attempting to move God's people forward in God's plan for the nations. This forward movement often occurred amid great world events and in the face of wicked, rebellious empires that opposed the kingdom of God. For modern people living 2500 years after Haggai and who are experiencing challenges on a global scale, it is encouraging to remember that confronting problems is not a new experience. It has always been that way. It always will be that way until the King returns and the kingdom he inaugurated in his first coming is consummated.

In 520 BC, the people of Israel had been back in the land and Jerusalem for 16 years. They were able to come back to the land because Cyrus the Great led the Persian military in a victorious campaign over the Babylonians. Unlike the policy of the Babylonians which exported people from ancestral lands into new territory, the Persians encouraged people to return to their

⁴ We find it a little bit in Zechariah but not with the consistency and precision as in Haggai.

homelands if they submitted to Persian authority. The decree that allowed the Jews to return is recorded in 2 Chronicles and Ezra and on a clay cylinder unearthed in 1879.⁵

The Jewish people began returning in 536 BC and were led by Zerubbabel, a grandson of King Jehoiachin and by Joshua, the grandson of the last high priest in Jerusalem. When they returned, one of their first projects was to rebuild the temple, but they did not start until 522 BC⁶ and did not complete this vital national and spiritual task. Instead, they continued focusing on building their homes and prospering their businesses. Jerusalem, before its destruction in 586 BC, had been a major market and trading center. After the Babylonian invasion and with the deportation of the population the land became mostly uncultivated and labor resources were limited. Some few who remained in the land after the Babylonian disaster built up wine and olive production, but life was hard for all. Despite these hardships, the people needed to rebuild the Temple and dedicate it as the center of their religious, social, and economic activity. God wanted the Temple in Jerusalem to be the center of everything so that the worship of the one true God would be the focal point of life. Only by re-establishing their worship could the nation of Israel be restored to what God intended and could his plan for the world go forward.

Some have suggested that political turmoil throughout the empire when Darius I became emperor (522 BC) prevented the rebuilding of the temple. However, if scholars are correct that Haggai should be dated at 520, the empire was at peace under Darius' firm control. In other words, there was no excuse for the temple of God to remain unbuilt.

⁵ "This barrel-shaped clay cylinder ... with a cuneiform inscription was buried in a 'foundation deposit' to commemorate building work done in Babylon by Cyrus. It tells about the Persians' capture of Babylon and Cyrus' policy of letting people return home. John Walton, OT Editor, *The NIV Cultural Background Study Bible*, Zondervan, Grand Rapids, MI, 2017, p. xxviii.

⁶ Mark J. Boda and J. Gordon McConville, *Dictionary of Old Testament Prophets*, "Book of Haggai," J. Kessler, IVP Academic, Downers Grove, IL, 2012, 303.

On August 29, 520 BC, God began his messages to this man.

- August 29 – 1:1-11 – The returned remnant must make the rebuilding of the temple its priority.
- September 21 – 1:12-15 – Zerubbabel, Joshua, and the people obey the voice of the prophet. God says he is with them.
- October 17 – 2:1-9 – Zerubbabel, Joshua, and the people should not be discouraged with the new temple. God will make it glorious.
- December 18 – 2:10-19 – God promises to reverse the fortunes of his people. Their scarcity will turn to abundance.
- December 18 – 2:20-23 – God will overthrow the kingdoms of this world and establish his kingdom.

Five brief messages in less than four months – that is Haggai – messages to a beleaguered people struggling to survive and to advance God’s kingdom plan for the world. It is a message for the Church today. God’s people must be faithful in the tasks to which he calls them, no matter how small. God’s people must not let discouragement hinder the work. God will use every effort of his people, and greatest of all, God’s kingdom will prevail in this world.

Philemon – Earthquake in the Empire

Was N.T. Wright stretching the point when he said about Philemon, “If we had no other first-century evidence for the movement that came to be called Christianity, this letter ought to make us think: Something is going on here. Something is different. People do not say this sort of thing. This isn’t how the world works.”⁷ Wright was comparing Paul’s letter to Philemon with Pliny the Younger’s letter to Sabinianus, a young friend dealing with a freed slave who has sought help from Pliny. Writing about 50 years after Paul penned Philemon, Pliny appeals to young Sabinianus to show mercy. Both letters speak of friendship. Both speak of obedience of

⁷ N.T. Wright, *Paul and the Faithfulness of God*, Fortress Press, Minneapolis, MN, 2013, 6.

the younger to the elder. But there, the similarities cease, and it is in the dissimilarities with the culture around that theological digging will find evidence of an ancient earthquake.

Paul's letter follows the basic epistolary structure:

- Salutation – 1:1-3
- Thanksgiving – 1:4-7
- Body of Letter and Paraenesis – 1:8-22
- Final Greeting with a Benediction – 1:23-25⁸

In the body of the letter, one finds six shock waves in the ancient world that reverberate to this day. The first shock wave pertains to status. Paul, like an aristocrat, writes to Philemon, and one can hear his authority and understand that Philemon would respect it. But the authority does not come from position as much as from moral example. Paul has touched Philemon's life and alludes to this in 1:19 when he says, "not to mention to you that you owe to me even yourself as well." But Paul is not a man who holds a position of power and esteem in the world. Paul is a prisoner in the Roman system! If, as Wright says, this letter was all one had, this fact alone should provoke the question, "How is it possible that a prisoner would wield such influence over a wealthy, free man like Philemon?"

The second shock wave also pertains to status, but from the other end. Paul the prisoner talks about Onesimus the slave. He gives the slave three titles. Onesimus has become his child (1:10). Paul sends him back to Philemon as his "very heart" (1:12), and he calls him Philemon's beloved brother (1:16). A slave is now a family member? A beloved brother? Freeing slaves did happen in the ancient world, and master-slave relationships could become close after decades of

⁸ Leland Ryken, *How to Read the Bible as Literature*, Zondervan, Grand Rapids, MI, 1984, 155. Ryken separates the body of the letter and the paraenesis thus creating five sections. But in Philemon, the body of the letter is the moral exhortation. Thus, Philemon, has four divisions rather than the standard five.

service,⁹ but this was a runaway slave who had probably incurred debt (1:19). The damage to Philemon was fresh. Yet, Paul speaks of a change in status. Why?

The third shock wave follows on the heels of the second. Paul asks Philemon to accept Onesimus as if he were accepting Paul himself! “If then you regard me a partner, accept him as you would me” (1:17). Even though Paul is in prison, he still wields moral authority in the letter. But now, he asks Philemon to give Onesimus the slave the same reception as if Paul himself were coming to visit!

The fourth shock wave is that Paul does not assert his authority. He appeals to Philemon. “Though I have enough confidence in Christ to order you to do what is proper, yet for love’s sake I rather appeal to you...” (1:9). Love instead of a command; an appeal instead of an order. What is going on in their world?

The fifth shock wave pertains to the speculation of what Onesimus might have done to Philemon. In some way, it seems, he has incurred debt (1:18). Perhaps it is only the debt of lost time and service. But Paul does not tell Philemon to allow Onesimus to pay off the debt. He says, “If he has wronged you in any way or owes you anything, charge that to my account.” Charge that to my account? Paul is going to pay the slave’s debt? Knowing NT theology, one can see incarnational and redemptive themes in Paul’s words. Christ entered this world and paid humanity’s unpayable debt. Paul is following in the footsteps of the humble, crucified Messiah.

The sixth and final shockwave is found in 1:21: “Having confidence in your obedience, I write to you, since I know that you will do even more than what I say.” What does he mean by “even more”? Paul has asked Philemon to receive Onesimus as if he were receiving Paul, to receive him as a beloved brother. He has also asked that Philemon allow Onesimus to return to

⁹ Notice the centurion in Matthew 8:5-13 (Luke 7:10) who wants Jesus to heal his servant.

Paul as his helper. What could the “even more” refer to? The strong possibility is that Paul is asking Philemon to set Onesimus free from his slavery.

Freeing slaves was not uncommon in the ancient world. But the way that Paul goes about it is different from the ancient and modern world. In the modern world, one looks at such a passage and says, “Of course Philemon should release him.” But this response does not consider the influence of the gospel upon modern life and that such obvious actions as freeing slaves were not so obvious and easy in the ancient world. In the ancient world, where would a freed slave go? What would he do to survive? Would he be better off as a freedman? We must recall that the prodigal son was not better off in his “freedom” than he was while “serving” his father. Philemon teaches that freedom is not the ultimate expression of the gospel. The ultimate expression, the goal of it all, is reconciliation. Paul does not order Philemon. Paul does not send Onesimus back to work off his debt or to right the record. Paul sends Onesimus back, no longer as a slave, but as his beloved child and Philemon’s beloved brother – reconciliation!

Four people stand in a circle with arms interlocked. Paul, Philemon, Onesimus, and the crucified Savior. Old relationships and structures have fallen away. A new reality, a new creation has entered the world – a reality of brotherhood that is made possible by the Messiah whose goal is to reconcile the world to himself and bring humanity together in the bonds of love.

1 John – Apostolic Apologetic

With sincere effort to bring assurance of salvation to people, 1 John 5:13 has often been quoted in evangelical circles, “Look at what John says,” the enthusiastic evangelist exudes. “‘I write these things to you who believe in the name of the Son of God so that you may know that you have eternal life.’ Do you see it? You can know that you have eternal life!” While not

inaccurate, and even while God has graciously used this verse and others like it to give assurance of salvation, this is not how John meant it to be used. 1 John was written in a complex situation to late first-century churches which were in danger from heretical influences. John Stott puts it this way: “It is not a theological treatise written in the academic peace of a library, but a tract for the times, called forth by a particular and urgent situation in the Church. This situation concerns the insidious propaganda of certain false teachers....”¹⁰

What were these false teachers promoting? 1 John reveals three issues: Illumination, Immorality, and Indifference. Illumination pertained to the idea that if people wanted to know God, they must pursue inner enlightenment, a special anointing, a revelation of the God who was within each person. This revelation would connect the person with the inner divinity to escape the corruption of the flesh. Those enlightened would one day ascend through astral realms to reconnect with deity. John addresses this in the following passages:

2:18-27	4:4-6	4:12-13, 15	5:9-15, 19-20
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Also, one finds John emphasizing the physical reality of Christ. The letter begins with concrete expressions of his full humanity, and this theme is sprinkled throughout the letter.

1:1-4	4:1-6	4:9-10, 14	5:6-8
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This proto-gnostic propaganda on physicality and the identity of the Messiah led to a second problem. If the body hindered true spirituality, one could go the route of asceticism or immorality because the body was not important. The false teachers afflicting John’s churches advocated the immorality route which is why John has several sections about righteous living.

1:5-2:6	2:15-17	2:28-3:12	3:24	5:3-5	5:16-18, 21
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¹⁰ John R.W. Stott, *The Epistles of John*, Eerdmans, Grand Rapids, MI, 1971, 41.

A final problem facing the churches was indifference. The proto-gnostic teaching favored the individual escaping to heavenly realms. Participating in a loving community on earth was no longer essential. John corrects this error by strongly appealing to the believers to love each other.

2:9-11	3:13-23	4:7-5:2
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This is the reason why John wrote his letter. He is giving a 3-fold checklist by which the churches could evaluate the true faith from one of many heresies infiltrating first-century Christian communities. The true faith taught that the man, Jesus of Nazareth, was the incarnation of the Eternal One. John’s first words were, “That which was from the beginning which we have heard, which we have seen with our eyes, which we have looked at and our hands have touched—this we proclaim....” He appeals to the senses: hearing, seeing, and touching. Jesus was not a phantom or spirit. He was a real flesh and blood human. Thus, John tells the churches to test the spirits. Every spirit that confesses that Jesus Christ has come in the flesh is from God. Those who do not confess this teaching are not from God (4:1-3). This was the first test.

The second and third tests pertained to righteousness and fellowship. If teachers were saying “It doesn’t matter how you live” and/or “You don’t need those other unenlightened people,” then one could know that they were not from God. Jesus himself commanded that believers should love one another (John 13:34-34-35 echoed in 2:7-11; 4:7-5:2). If people are not living morally and saying that they know God and that their actions are not sinful, then one could be certain that they are not from the Father (1:5-2:6; 2:15-17; 2:28-3:12).

Lest the reader thinks this is only a history lesson, it must be pointed out that the applications for today’s Christian are pertinent and profound. Believers must adhere to the historic, apostolic doctrine faithfully carried on by their successors and outlined in their historic creeds. The creeds were written to give precise summaries of apostolic faith to stand against the

never-ending heresies seeking to siphon believers from the community that Christ established. Believers must live moral lives as a testimony to the importance of God's creation. The body does matter. The body is not secondary or unimportant. This world in which God's people live is not secondary to some far-off spiritual nirvana. How one treats creation is vital, and the hope of the faith is for the renewal of creation, not its abolition. Living immorally and unrighteously brings destruction. Living righteously is of God because God is light and in him is no darkness at all (1:5). Just as he is pure, so the believer must pursue purity (3:3). This kind of life cannot be done in isolation. Believers must unite in community. Loving one another is not a nice idea. It is Jesus' command (2:7-11).

How then should one understand John's words, "These things I have written to you that you may know that you have eternal life." On the one hand, John's words in 5:13 were not written to give assurance of salvation to someone who just prayed the sinner's prayer or even to encourage a believer stumbling in doubt (although it is not a heresy to use them that way!). They were written as a summary of John's 3-fold test by which his readers could know the difference between those adhering to apostolic teaching – and thus had eternal life – and those who had succumbed to deceptive twists of that teaching – and thus were on a path of darkness leading to death. On the other hand, John's words in 5:13 were written so that readers through the ages could know the solid foundation upon which their eternal life rested. It is a solid foundation upon which we may build our lives in the 21st century – a foundation of true knowledge, a foundation of righteous living, and a foundation of a loving community.

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